

Sustainable Development and Women's rights in Pakistan – A Paradigmatic Analysis

Vol. 2, No. I (2017) | Page: 63 – 69 | DOI: 10.31703/grr.2017(II-I).05

p-ISSN: 2616-955X | e-ISSN: 2663-7030 | L-ISSN: 2616-955X

Muhammad Zia-ur-Rehman* Muzamil Shah† Muhammad Usman Ullah‡

Abstract

“Human rights” is essential for a dignified existence. It is a truth universally acknowledged, that women make up around half of the total population, yet at the same time they are disregarded. Reasonable and practical steps are vital for the development as a nation. In Human Rights, a neglected aspect is “Women’s rights” which is not neglected in academia but in practical life. The paper focuses on the existing circumstance of women’s rights generally and the circumstances of women’s rights in Pakistan particularly. The study examines present conditions and circumstances, where women face various issues. Conclusively, seven essential recommendations are made for women’s rights in public as well as in private organizations for a balanced society with sustainable development.

Key Words: Human Rights, Sustainable development goals, UNDP, Women Rights, Pakistan

The situation

As we know that women make 50 % of the population. In 2000, UNDP made women’s rights a focal issue to be considered fundamentally all over the world. Different endeavors have been made to manage women’s rights as issue all-inclusive. In the Convention on the Elimination of all types of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) in 1996, there was adequate hope for women’s rights. And women’s rights activists saw the improvement as a noteworthy triumph for women.

* Assistant Professor, Department of Leadership & Management Studies, National Defence University, Islamabad, Pakistan. Email: drziaemail@gmail.com

† Department of Law, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, Mardan, KP, Pakistan.

‡ Junior Research Fellow, Humanity Research Council, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Pakistan

Pakistan tried to deal with human rights issues at its own. In Human Rights Council at the United Nations, Pakistan's delegation attempts and sets up a courageous front in protecting the nation's human rights record. Pakistan has also marked numerous critical UN conventions attempting to actualize the women's rights locally. But what actually is the situation?

Human Rights Perspective

From one Human Rights Perspective, Pakistan's by and large financial markers were practically identical with rising economies in general, but its social markers have been falling behind even Nepal and Bhutan.

From another Human Rights Perspective, It has been noticed that Pakistan is exceptionally poor as far as water quality regardless of various activities at the government level. The markers have gone down definitely in the course of the last 10-15 years coming about contrarily on wellbeing and sustenance. Poor water quality emerged out of untreated modern waste streaming into drinking water resources, causing expanded pervasiveness of hepatitis, improper growth and different diseases (Jamal & Amina. 2005).

Still from another Human Rights Perspective, if truth be told, this seemed to come down to administrative issue as lodging social orders and enterprises extended without arranging in every single significant city, leaving waste mechanical water and sewerage squander into trenches and channels of water, influencing urban foundation (Ansari, & Sarfraz, 2011).

From yet another Human Rights Perspective, the issue exists at the very basic level which was noted is no focus and allocation of administrative and budgetary forces of the locale governments (Chaudhary, et al., 2011).

Pakistanis are battling poverty, imbalance and bad form of governance, and taking care of the aftermath from environmental change.

From Women's Rights Perspectives

Is a universally acknowledged fact that women make around 50% of the population? The alarming condition is that women's absence of education in country territories, further affects the low status as women in any country.

Sustainable development goals are established in order to gauge the progress of countries on a scale and thus put them in ranking and rating (Saigol, Rubina, 2016). However, Paksitan has made commitment in meeting the 17 sustainable development goals with destinations to building the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) but the reality is not very hopeful (Noureen, 2011).

As far as Pakistan is concerned, the Gender Gap Index 2015 positioned Pakistan second from the bottom among 145 nations.

Pakistan verified a score on Sustainable Development Goals of 55.6 under against a far higher provincial normal of 63.3 and is even lower than territorial friends Bangladesh's 56.2 and India's 58.1. (Sohail, 2014).

Along these lines, the country situated 122 on the SDG rundown of 157 nations diverged from Bangladesh's 120 and India's 116 position, according to July 2017 results. The financial issues have an immediate bearing on women lives in Pakistani society. All inclusive, Pakistan's positioning in the Mother Mortality Ratio (MMR) slipped to 149 from 147 – only just after Afghanistan – as indicated by the State of the World's Mothers 2015 report by Save the Children.

Women issues in Pakistan include; lack of education, nourishment, instability, deficient sustenance, low monetary allocation, high security concerns, which actually have been referred to as hindrances when meeting Millennium Development Goals (MDG) targets (Tertilt, & Doepke, 2010).

Almost 50 % of the nation's population who are not full members in the domain of financial advancement, then how come a nation be successful in developing itself in order to compete in the world community.

What Forms Women are denied of the Equivalent Rights?

- Work discrimination: occupations
- Systematic denial
- Public organizations: the discrimination in public responsibilities
- Private organizations: consideration of women in private organisations and business ventures.
- Legal surety: legal security need exists
- Socially: sexual violence, abuse, household work unpaid and uncounted burden,
- Financial aspects: monetary responsibility issue
- Women status – not considering a socially equal to men

Recommendations

Based on the above discussion and analysis, the following recommendations are made:

Recommendation 1:

There is a need to create awareness about the constitution of the country, with its implementation in true sense. The constitution of Pakistan ensures equal rights for

every one of its natives without discrimination. It additionally guarantees full interest of women in all circles of life.

Recommendation 2:

Featuring Vision of Pakistan 2025 and then vision 2030 as the blue print for Pakistan's own long-term planning for sustainable and comprehensive development.

Recommendation 3:

Some special consideration and programs, which may be not popular, are to be initiated. Some uncommon Schemes like 'Women Employment Scheme' and alike are of great support for motivating women to be part of the mainstream.

Recommendation 4:

A National Financial Inclusion Strategy should be initiated. There are more than fifty organizations in Pakistan, which are giving credit and micro scale credit offices to women with ideas to start business.

Recommendation 5:

Pakistan needs a mission for SDG usage, which has to be brought down to the lowest grounds by means of the Local government framework (LGFs).

Recommendation 6:

Infrastructure and systems are to be established. Surprisingly, there is a need for general mindfulness. Women's rights cannot be safeguarded and also, they cannot be brought to play their productive role in the mainstream until and unless structure and system not established. E.g. not having washrooms was affecting female training and study even.

Recommendation 7:

There is need to understand the true concept of the Complete code of life, that's Islam as Islam provides thorough guidelines on not only equal but also special consideration to women's rights on both economic and social grounds. History is full of examples; Arabs before Islam, era of Jahaliya, Babylonians, Egyptians, and other societies have been worse for women. History shows that they used to burry young girls, and women were considered as evil spirit or just as a slave of man. I

would make my submission here that please don't judge what Muslims do but read the authentic sources of Islam; Quran and Hadith, where its ordained that both men and women are equal but not identical – based on biological, physiological, and psychological make ups, they are different. The creator has created them different. In Islam, women were given rights 1400 year ago in a comprehensive manner as women' rights in Islam based on: spiritual, economic, social, educational, legal, political grounds.

Conclusively, none of us can develop and progress if half of us are abandoned or lagging behind due to discrimination. Napoleon Said, “give me an educated mother, I shall promise you the birth of a civilized educated nation”.

References

- Ansari, Sarfraz. 2011. "Forced Modernization and Public Policy: A Case Study of Ayub Khan Era (1958-69)". *Journal of Political Studies* 18, no. 1:45-60. Assessed June 1, 2012. http://scholar.googleusercontent.com/scholar?q=cache:xTwdNuzcgxkJ:scholar.google.com/++role+of+women+in+ayub+era+&hl=en&as_sdt=0,5
- "Britain's unwritten constitution". British Library. Retrieved 27 November 2015. The key landmark is the Bill of Rights (1689), which established the supremacy of Parliament over the Crown ... providing for the regular meeting of Parliament, free elections to the Commons, free speech in parliamentary debates, and some basic human rights, most famously freedom from 'cruel or unusual punishment. "Norms on the responsibilities of transnational corporations and other business enterprises with regard to human rights". UN Sub-Commission on the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights. Retrieved 3 January 2008.
- Chaudhary A. R., Chani, M. I., & Pervez, Z. (2011). An Analysis of different Approaches to Women Empowerment: A Case study of Pakistan. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 16(7), 971-980.
- Development Economics, Pakistan. Series #26. Pakistan.
- Discourses In Pakistan". *Meridians: feminism, race, transnationalism*, 5, no. 2: 57-82. Assessed June 15, 2012. <http://muse.jhu.edu/login?auth=0&type=summary&url=/journals/meridians/v005/5.2jamal.html> <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3874341>
- Jafar, Afshan. 2005. "Women , Islam and the State in Pakistan". *Gender Issues* 22, no.1: 35-55. Assessed June 7, 2012. doi:10.1007/s12147-005-0009-z
- Jamal ,Amina. 2005. "Feminist 'Selves' And Feminism's 'Others': Feminist Representations Of Jamaat-E-Islami Women". *Feminist Review*, no. 81: 52-73. Assessed June 10, 2012.
- Jamal, Amina. 2005. "Transnational Feminism As Critical Practice: A Reading Of Feminist
- Noureen, G (2011). Women's Education in Pakistan: Hidden Fences on Open Frontiers. *Asian Social Sciences*, 7(2), p.79.

- Nyazee, Imran Ahsan. 2014. "The Council of Islamic Ideology (CII) and Child Marriage." SSRN, Last Modified 5 November, accessed 5 September. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2519471
- Saigol, Rubina. 2016. *Feminism and the Women's Movement in Pakistan: Actors, Debates and Strategies*. Islamabad: Friedrich Ebert Stiftung.
- Sathar, Z. and S. Desai. 1996. "Work Patterns in Rural Pakistan: Intersections Between Gender, Family, and Class." Working Paper No. 90, Research Division.
- Sathar, Z. and S. Kazi. 1997. "Women's Autonomy, Livelihood and Fertility." Pakistan Institute of
- Shaheed, F. and K. Mumtaz. 1990. "Women's Participation in Pakistan."
- Shaheed, F. et al. 1998. "Women in Politics: Participation and Representation in Pakistan." *Shirkat Gah, Pakistan*.
- Sohail, M. (2014) Women Empowerment and Economic Development—an Exploratory Study in Pakistan. *Developing Countries Study*, 4(9), 163-170.
- Tertilt, M., & Doepke, M. (2010). Does Female Empowerment Promote Economic Development? In 2010 Meeting Papers (No. 230). USA: Society for Economic Dynamics.